

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.3 - Project website with manual

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofunded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document summarizes the design, the structure and management of ePLANET project website, available at www.eplaneth2020.eu.

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1 Website description

The main objective of the website is to serve as the vehicle for the communication and dissemination of project activities and outcomes, complementarily to the social media channels. This document summarizes the design and management of ePLANET project website, available at www.eplaneth2020.eu.

While the website has been publicly available since mid-November 2021, with an initial simple version (“home” and “our project” sections), the version at the end of December 2021 is already fully operational.

The ePLANET website has been defined to be user-friendly and easy to use, with a smooth transition between the different sections and some transversal functionalities (e.g. social networks, contact form, news, language) that are present in different sections.

1.1 Languages

The ePLANET project is targeting local authorities across Europe, but with special emphasis in the 3 pilot regions: Catalonia, Crete island and Zlín region. So, while English will be the main communication and dissemination language, the website includes specific sections in Catalan, Greek and Czech languages to facilitate communication and dissemination in those regions.

1.2 Website structure

The website includes a tree structure following the 5 main sections to facilitate an easy access to the most useful information. Thus, the main sections defined in the website are:

Home - Our project - News - Resources - ePLANET platform - Contact

1.2.1 Home

The “Home” section includes some leitmotiv style description of ePLANET project ambition, followed by a summary of the news section (highlighting the 3 most recent news). A newsletter subscription form has also be included, in order to allow visitors to receive the periodic newsletter that the project will prepare.

1.2.2 Our project

The “Our Project” section allows the understanding of the ePLANET goals, objectives and impacts. A part from those aspects, this section includes also a visual representation of the target groups and stakeholders and the description of the three demo-sites. A Consortium description is also included, with links to the partners institutional webpages.

1.2.3 News

This section keeps the visitor informed about all the events and news of the project. The section includes a matrix-style view of the different news, chronologically sorted. A widget to follow ePLANET twitter is also included, as well as the newsletter subscription form to allow visitors to receive the regular newsletters the project will prepare.

1.2.4 Resources

This section allows to easy find all the public documentation created within the ePLANET project. From public deliverables to scientific papers or conference presentations, as well as webinars & workshops recordings (in direct link to the ePLANET YouTube channel).

1.2.5 ePLANET platform

This section will allow stakeholders to get access to the ePLANET platform that will be developed within WP3. So, at the moment of writing this document, the structure of this section is still under definition. We expect this section to be made public once the platform will be created, following WP3 progress.

1.2.6 Contact, social media and newsletter subscription

The website includes the usual contact section, together with specific high visibility icons to follow the project progress through the social media channels (in particular Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube).

The newsletter subscription form has been also included, in order to allow interested stakeholders to receive the regular newsletters that the project will create during its duration.

2 Website screenshots

Several screenshots of the website are included within this document. The whole website can be accessed through: www.eplaneth2020.eu .

Figure 2-1 - "Home" section (partial view)

Figure 2-2 - "Our Project" section (partial view)

Figure 2-3 - "News" section (partial view)

ePLANET Home Our project **News**

Project leaflets already available!
Dec 16, 2021
We are happy to announce that we have designed the project leaflet, with a brief explanation about ePLANET project goals and expected impact.

Clustering governance
Nov 24, 2021
One of the main challenges to achieve #EnergyTransition is to improve the coordination between local authorities and regional governments in order to optimise the decision-making process...

Launch of ePLANET project to accelerate the Energy Transition in European municipalities
Sep 29, 2021
The European ePLANET project will use a new clustering governance strategy together with the most innovative tools in artificial intelligence...

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Figure 2-4 - "Partner description" section (partial view)

The screenshot displays the 'Partner description' section of the ePLANET project website. At the top left is the ePLANET logo, and at the top right are navigation links for 'Home', 'Our project', and 'News'. The main heading is 'CIMNE – International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering', accompanied by the CIMNE logo. Below this, a paragraph describes CIMNE as a leading research and technological development institution. A second paragraph states that CIMNE is the project coordinator and responsible for the ePLANET platform development. The 'Other Partners' section follows, featuring a grid of logos for various partners: ICLEI, CIMNE, THREE CLOCK, REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND OF CRETE, LIMA, KAPE CRES, Diputació de Girona, ea, FEDARENE, and Generalitat de Catalunya Institut Català d'Eners.

ePLANET

Home Our project News

CIMNE – International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering

CIMNE
International Centre
for Numerical Methods in Engineering

The **International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE)** is a leading research and technological development institution with a proven ability to deliver big data management services in energy, building and environment fields.

In ePLANET, CIMNE is the project coordinator, technology provider and responsible for the ePLANET platform development. The EU project ePLANET is a logical progress of CIMNE BEE Group's dedicated department, providing innovative solutions for local public authorities to drive them in the Energy Transition.

Other Partners

